

Inferring transportation modes from user-generated street view videos

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Summary

This work investigates the potential of analysing user-generated street view imagery from videos to extract transportation modes, for example whether individuals are walking or cycling, using deep neural-networks. It addresses existing data gaps with respect to monitoring the sustainability of the mix of transport modes in cities, and complements existing methods based on stationary count stations or Google Street View. Preliminary results show the potential of the proposed workflow to automatically extract forms of transportation from videos as alternative data form.

KEYWORDS: street-view imagery, videos, transportation modes, neural-networks

1. Introduction

Knowing how people get around in urban areas is important for building, improving and monitoring the transportation mode composition in cities around the world. Street View Imagery (SVI) as entrenched component of urban analytics is used extensively to approximate mobility through volumes of pedestrians (Yin, Cheng, Wang, & Shao, 2015), cyclist (Wang, Lu, Wu, Liu, & Yao, 2020) and cars (den Braver, et al., 2020) detected in urban environments. The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11.2 emphasises the importance of sustainable modes of transportation in urban areas, but currently indicator 11.2.1 only measures ‘access to public transportation’ ignoring any other sustainable alternatives such as cycling and walking.

The current scientific literature on the remote-sensing counter part SVI is dominated by work that uses Google Street View (GSV) imagery (Biljecki & Ito, 2021). In this work, I leverage virtual city tour videos from video sharing providers such as YouTube or Vimeo that capture first-person street-view imagery to measure transportation modes. These videos gained in popularity due to globally imposed travel restrictions as a consequence of the Covid pandemic. They provide sequences of images with potentially higher spatial and temporal resolution compared to GSV, in areas less accessible by car (e.g. parks, shopping arcades). A selection of these videos are under Creative Commons licensing which allows their use for scientific purposes without conflicting with terms and conditions of services, an issue often ignored by applications using GSV. I want to investigate the potential of this data source given its absence in the recent scientific literature review “Street view imagery in urban analytics and GIS” by (Biljecki & Ito, 2021) to complement urban transportation mode distribution measurements where current forms of monitoring, GSV and stationary count stations lack coverage.

2. Methods

The extraction of transportation mode counts from videos is divided into three parts. The first part being the detection and tracking of mobility relevant objects (e.g. bicycles, cars, people) across frames. Hereby, the deep neural-network Yolov5 (Jocher, et al., 2021) is used for object detection, whereas the DeepSort framework (Wojke, Bewley, & Paulus, 2017) is used for object tracking. Secondly, active transportation modes have to be assigned to the detected objects. This process involves differentiating between, for instance stationary bicycles and ones that a person is currently riding. This is achieved by analysing the spatial relationship of the objects across multiple frames and matching them to

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transportation mode specific characteristics. Lastly, the results are geolocated in space. Since the videos are not natively georeferenced, street names are detected with Object Character Recognition (OCR), implemented with the EasyOCR codebase (JaidedAI, 2022) and compared to an Open Street Map (OSM) compiled street name gazetteer.

3. Results

So far the project is in the prototype phase but fully functional. I tested the current workflow on a 5min excerpt from an exemplary YouTube video[†] with a total of 9000 frames that covers the old town of Geneva, Switzerland in November 2020. The workflow detected a variety of mobility related objects (see **Table 1**) including 41 cars, 13 motor- and 40 bicycles. From these objects, the workflow inferred transportation modes. It detected only two types, pedestrians (90) and cyclists (6) since the remaining relevant objects (e.g. motorcycles) were not driven by a person at the time but parked. A manual evaluation found 78 pedestrians and 5 cyclists which fits well. The georeferencing step returned one match based on an OCR detected street name “Rue de l’Hôtel-de-Ville”, which was correct and allowed the video to be roughly allocated in space.

Figure 1 Video frame[†] with visualised object tracking ids used for inferring transportation modes. The constellation of object id 56 and 67 match the one of a cyclist.

Table 1 Detected results by our workflow and manual counting

Objects	Count	Transportation modes	Count	True Count
persons	96	pedestrians	90	78
bicycles	40	cyclists	6	5
cars	41	car drivers	0	1
motorcycles	13	motorcyclists	0	0
buses	1	bus passengers	0	0

[†] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BE-lyw7MgHU&t=321s>

4. Discussion and Conclusion

No existing projects in the scientific literature were found that use Street View Imagery from user-generated videos for urban analytics. Our preliminary results show that this alternative data source shows potential to measure forms of transportation such as pedestrians and cyclists while simultaneously providing georeferencing through street names. Looking at the data gap in SDG indicator 11.2.1, my work could complement existing measurements to quantify sustainable transportation in urban environments by detecting the mobility mix in areas less accessible by car or outside the main transportation nodes. The ability for the proposed methodology to automatically analyse an entire collection of videos allows simple upscaling which would not be possible for comparable manual analysis.

Future work will extend the research area to cover an entire city. In addition, the individual workflow components need to be further trained and different OCR algorithms will be tested to improve the street name detection accuracy as well as the high computational demand currently involved in this step.

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Biography

Maximilian C. Hartmann is a PhD student in the Geocomputation unit at the Geography department of the University of Zurich, Switzerland. He received a master's degree in Environmental Science at the ETH Zurich. His current field of study placement is within VGIScience, which works with Volunteered Geographic Information for dominantly landscape perception studies.